

Entropy Based on Probabilities Affecting Measurements Being Made?

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Boltzmann's definition of entropy $S = -k \ln(\text{number of states})$, suggests that states must be identified by certain measurable characteristics. One may consider a superset of identifiers or a subset and hence obtain different values of entropy. The idea in the literature, however, seems to be that one tries to consider the maximum number of identifiers in order to obtain the maximum entropy. In particular, there are complaints that the von Neumann entropy is zero for a pure state (e.g. energy eigenstate) when there are momentum and position uncertainties within this eigenstate which can lead to a calculable Shannon's entropy (1). In the case of the Shannon entropy definition, one begins with probabilities, and so the entropy obtained depends on the probabilities used.

We have suggested in previous notes that one may consider entropy based on the measurement being made. Here we wish to clarify this by noting that there may be various sets of probabilities for different variables in a problem. If one chooses to measure a subset of these variables, some or all of the probabilities present may be involved. We consider two examples, photons being absorbed and emitted by an atom and spatial entropy for the same problem. Overall, there is probability for a photon to be emitted/absorbed, but also internal momentum and spatial probability for any given energy eigenstate. The latter two probabilities do not influence photon absorption/emission (rather they are influenced by it), so if one wishes to measure only the energy level probability, these two internal probabilities do not affect the energy eigenstate measurement and may be ignored in such an entropy calculation. On the other hand, if one wishes to measure spatial entropy, then the probability of being in a certain energy eigenstate is a factor as are the $a^*(p)a(p)$ and $W^*(x)W(x)$ based internal probabilities, where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction for state n (energy) and $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$. Thus, the probabilities (and hence related) states which affect the stochasticity of a particular measurement are to be considered in an entropy calculation which is hence measurement based. In other words, entropy in a problem is not necessarily a universal concept. We argue that being able to identify that particular probabilities and their effects on measurements is key. We further argue that it is possible to have probability which contributes nothing to entropy depending on what is being measured.

A Free Moving Particle with Constant Speed

Quantum mechanics suggests that a free moving particle with constant E and p is linked with spatial and temporal probability, i.e. $\exp(-iEt)$, $\exp(ipx)$. E and p are completely certain and so there is no sense of any probability associated with measurements of these, i.e. no associated entropy. There is spatial and temporal uncertainty, but these affect interactions the particle might make in space and time. A free moving particle has a deterministic trajectory $x=vt$ and makes no special interactions and so $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$, although they exist, are not involved in affecting any measurements and there is no entropy associated with them.

This scenario, however, changes if a 2-slit apparatus is introduced into space. Then, $\exp(ipx)$ leads to uncertainty in an interaction (which is a kind of measurement) and results in an

entangled state, i.e. $\exp(i p r_1) + \exp(i p r_2)$ with r_1 and r_2 lying in different direction in x-y space. The deterministic $x=vt$ is no gone and even though E and $|p|$ are certain, the direction of p is not. In this case, $\exp(ipx)$ leads to an entropy in space, but also to a directional p entropy for each x point on a screen far away from the 2-slit apparatus.

A second example is one dimensional reflection-refraction at an n_1 - n_2 (index of refraction) junction. A photon has p (if incident) , $-p$ if reflected and p_2 if refracted. There is a certain probability to reflect and refract, but these are due directly to the probability $\exp(ipx)$ which, together, with its first derivative, must be continuous at the junction, i.e.

$$A \exp(ipx) + B \exp(-ipx) = C \exp(ip_2x) \text{ at } x=0 \quad ((1a))$$

$$A p \exp(ipx) + B (-p) \exp(-ipx) = C p_2 \exp(ip_2x) \text{ at } x=0 \quad ((1b))$$

Thus, $\exp(ipx)$ is a probability directly associated with a particular interaction and so is the underlying uncertainty behind the entropy in this situation. The entropy itself is actually calculated using probability to reflect = B^*B and probability to refract = C^*C with $A=1$. Thus, $\exp(ipx)$ is not directly used in a Shannon's entropy calculation, but leads directly to the calculation of the B and C values needed. These are linked to the probabilities that are actually measured, but are obtained from $\exp(ipx)$. In other words, a probability linked to a measurement may be fully or partially based on other probabilities existing in the problem. Thus, one cannot blindly insert any probability present into a Shannon's entropy expression.

Entropy of a Quantum Energy Eigenstate

We have noted that a free particle has a constant E, p , but also associated interaction probabilities $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ that only manifest themselves in certain interactions. There is in addition, the free particle trajectory $x=vt$ which suggests that all x points have the same probability.

What happens then in quantum bound state? The particle interacts with $V(x)$ such that E and p values change from one free value set to another. Thinking classically, one would argue that between interactions with the potential, the particle moves freely according to $x=vt$. (In classical statistical mechanics, it moves free according to $dp/dt = -dV/dx$ as one does not consider free motion.) Quantum mechanics, however, suggests that interactions are governed by $\exp(ipx)$ and so one cannot think in terms of a hit and then free motion. Rather, interactions are governed by the probability $\exp(ipx)$. Average energy must be conserved at each x point and this gives momentum weights $a(p)$ to each $\exp(ipx)$. Thus, there are two sets of interrelated probabilities $\exp(ipx)$ and $a(p)$, but the measurement probabilities (similar to the one dimensional reflection-refraction case) are:

$$W^*(x)W(x) \text{ and } a^*(p)a(p) \text{ where } W(x) = \text{Sumover } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx) \quad ((2))$$

Again $\exp(ipx)$ and $a(p)$ are probabilities used to calculate the probabilities $W^*(x)W(x)$ and $a^*(p)a(p)$ used in measurement and which define a spatial entropy density and momentum

entropy density. We suggest adding the two entropies, one integrated over space and the other over momentum because they are not independent.

Like the free particle case which has a certain E, p , but uncertainties in $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$, a certain E_{ave} for a bound state is linked with an entropy. (We have suggested in a previous note trying to create an entropy measure for $\exp(-iEt)$, $\exp(ipx)$, but this is not discussed here.) Given that a quantum energy eigenstate is associated with momentum and spatial entropy, does this mean that this entropy and $W^*(x)W(x)$ and $a^*(p)a(p)$ must appear in Shannon entropy calculations involving the bound state? We consider this question in the next section.

Photon Absorption/Emission from Quantum Bound States

Physically, one may consider photons being absorbed from quantum bound states in a statistical manner. In other words, there is $P(E_n)$, a probability to be in a certain energy state E_n . This may be measured. The question becomes: What probabilities or uncertainties lead to $P(E_n)$? Each E_n state contains entropy, i.e. momentum and spatial probabilities $a^*(p)a(p)$ for n and $W^*(x)W(x)$ for n , but these may have no effect on whether a photon is absorbed or emitted and hence no effect on $P(E_n)$. In other words, one is interested in an entropy associated with the measurement of E_n and only probabilities affecting this lead to such a measurement based entropy. As a result, one uses the usual classical weights of $\exp(-E_n/T)$ in a photon absorption/emission problem, ignoring the probabilities $W_n^*(x)W_n(x)$ and $a_n^*(p)a_n(p)$ which have no effect on the measurement of E_n .

Spatial Entropy of a Quantum System with Photon Absorption/Emission

What if one wishes to calculate the spatial entropy of a quantum atom absorbing and emitting photons? In such a case, different E_n states have different $W_n^*(x)W_n(x)$ and $a_n^*(p)a_n(p)$ values and so one must make use of all probabilities, i.e., $P(E_n) = \exp(-E_n/T)$ as well as $W_n^*(x)W_n(x)$. $a_n(p)$ is already built into $W_n(x)$. Thus, the entropy calculation in question is based on a certain measurement which in turn is associated with different probabilities which affect it. One does not, it seems, simply use all probabilities available to calculate a generic entropy representing all possible states possible.

Quantum Particle in an Infinite Well

Classically, a particle with constant $E = p^2/2m$ in a box has a position uncertainty of $P(x)dx = dx/L$, where L is the length of the one dimensional box. This is consistent with the trajectory $x = vt$, i.e. the particle spends the same dt at each dx .

Quantum mechanically, the wavefunction $W_n(x)$ is 0 at $x=0$ and $x=L$ (or $-L/2$ to $L/2$) which means there is a superposition (or entangled state) of all $\exp(ipx)$ s. In other words, there is a momentum entropy linked with $a_n^*(p)a_n(p)$. Spatially, one has $\exp(ipx)$ s, but like in the free particle case, there is no interaction in space (no 2-slit apparatus etc). As a result, even though there is a probability $\exp(ipx)$ and the overall wavefunction $W_n(x) = C \sin(p_{ave} x)$ where $p_{ave} = n\pi/L$, there are no interactions in space associated with $\exp(ipx)$. As a result, one might

speculate that the spatial entropy does not depend on n (energy level) even though there is a clear $\sin(\text{pave}(n) x)$ pattern. It is simply not being measured like in the case of a free particle. As a result, (1) shows that Shannon's spatial entropy, using:

$$P_n(x,t) = 2/L (\sin(kn(x-x_c+L/2))) \text{ for } x_c-L/2 < x < x_c+L/2 \quad ((3))$$

0 elsewhere

leads to a Shannon's entropy - $\int dx P_n(x) \ln(P_n(x)) = \ln(2L/e x_0) \quad ((4))$

where x_0 is an arbitrary length.

A classical calculation uses $P(x)dx = dx/L$ or $-\int dx 1/L \ln(1/L) = \ln(L) \quad ((5))$

which is very similar to the quantum result. Both are completely independent of the energy level, i.e. average speed/momentum. Thus, the presence of a spatial probability in $\sin(\text{pave}(n) x)$ is not enough to affect entropy because there are no interactions in space involving $\exp(ipx)$ unlike the case of a $V(x)$ which is not 0 in space.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that there may be many probabilities present in a system which may or may not contribute to a probability linked to a particular measurement being made. We argue that Shannon's entropy - $k \sum_i P(i) \ln(P(i))$, where i is a measurement state, uses the probability for the measurement i . One must consider all probabilities/uncertainties present in the system to determine which contribute to $P(i)$. In general, not all will and so using a set $P(i)$ yields an entropy value associated with a particular measurement.

In some cases, probabilities may be associated with certain values and so there is no entropy even though there is probability. A free particle with a constant E, p , but with quantum $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ as uncertainty which is not being manifested. Hence the entropy of E, p may be thought of as 0. As soon as the particle, however, interacts with a 2-slit system, then $\exp(ipx)$ becomes associated with an entropy as an entangled state is created.

A quantum bound state has probabilities linked with $W_n^*(x)W_n(x)$ and $a_n^*(p)a_n(p)$, but these probabilities have no impact, it seems on photon emission/absorption. Thus, if one has a photons interacting with an atom, then $P(E_n)$ (measured) does not depend on $W_n^*(x)W_n(x)$ or $a_n^*(p)a_n(p)$ and $P(E_n) = \exp(-E_n/T) C$, (C =normalization constant), i.e. the usual classical result. Spatial entropy, however, depends on $P(E_n)$ and $W_n^*(x)W_n(x)$. Thus, one must be aware of the specific probabilities which combine to create the probability of a variable being measured and entropy only pertains to that kind of measurement, we argue.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Particle_in_a_box